

**The comparative analysis and characteristics of phraseologisms and idioms in
Uzbek and English languages**

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola leksikologiyaning frazeologiyaga oid bo‘limiga bag‘ishlanigan bo‘lib, unda ingliz va o‘zbek tillaridagi kiyim-kechak nomlari ishtirok etgan frazeologik va idiomatik birliklar lingvomadaniy jihatdan qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Shu bilan bir qatorda, har bir millatning mentaliteti, madaniyati, urf-odatlar va an‘analarini yaqqol ifodalovchi frazeologik vositalarning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari ikki til (ingliz va o‘zbek tillari) nuqtai nazaridan ochib berilgan, hamda frazeologik birliklar haqida muhim ma‘lumotlar taqdim etiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: lingvomadaniy, idiomatik ifoda, leksikologiya, madaniyatlararo muloqot, kognitiv yondashuv, tushunchaviy sohalar, frazeologik birliklar.

Annotation: This article is dedicated to the section of lexicology concerning phraseology. It presents a comparative linguacultural analysis of phraseological and idiomatic units involving clothing names in English and Uzbek. Additionally, the specific features of phraseological expressions that vividly reflect the mentality, culture, customs, and traditions of each nation are revealed from the perspective of both languages (English and Uzbek). The article also provides important information about phraseological units.

Keywords: linguacultural, idiomatic expression, lexicology, intercultural communication, cognitive approach, conceptual domains, phraseological units.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена разделу лексикологии, связанному с фразеологией. В ней проводится сопоставительный лингвокультурный анализ фразеологических и идиоматических единиц с названиями одежды в английском и узбекском языках. Также раскрываются особенности фразеологических средств, ярко отражающих менталитет, культуру, обычаи и традиции каждого народа с точки зрения двух языков (английского и узбекского). В статье также представлены важные сведения о фразеологических единицах.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурный, идиоматическое выражение, лексикология, межкультурная коммуникация, когнитивный подход, сферы концептов, фразеологические единицы.

Linguacultural study is an interdisciplinary science that has developed at the crossroads of cultural studies and linguistics. It investigates the complex relationship between language and culture, including how this connection originates, evolves, and manifests both within language structures and in broader social contexts. Linguacultural studies aim to uncover how culture influences language use and how language, in turn, reflects cultural identity and worldview. On the one hand, it explores how human experience is embedded in linguistic expressions shaped by cultural norms, and on the other hand, how individuals interact with and interpret language through the lens of their cultural background.

Every language serves not only as a means of communication but also as a repository of a nation's historical memory, traditional lifestyle, values, geographical environment, and collective notions many of which are subtly encoded in idioms and expressions. Thus, language becomes a mirror of a people's way of life. Foreign language learners often face challenges in fully understanding the deeper meanings behind phraseological expressions of another culture until they acquire knowledge of that culture's traditions, social behaviours, and patterns of thought [1]. Although a substantial amount of research has been devoted to the grammatical, semantic, and syntactic analysis of phraseological units, their study from a linguacultural perspective examining how cultural elements are embedded in these expressions remains relatively underdeveloped. Expanding this area of research is essential for a fuller understanding of intercultural communication and effective language learning.

The intrinsic connection between language and culture was first articulated by the German scholar Wilhelm Humboldt, who asserted that a person's language reflects the world in a way that brings it to life. He emphasized that language embodies the identity of its speakers, encapsulating their way of life and cultural worldview [2].

Later, prominent scholars such as M.M.Pokrovsky, G.V.Stepanov, A.A.Potebnya, D.S.Likhachev, Y.M.Lotman, and F.I.Busayev contributed significantly to the development of linguocultural studies, laying the theoretical and scientific foundation for this field. In Uzbek linguistics, pioneering contributions to linguocultural studies were made by researchers such as Sh.Safarov, D.Khudoyberganov, N.Mahmudov, and Sh.Usmanova. More recently, the comparative study of Uzbek phraseology with other languages from a linguocultural and cognitive perspective has gained dominance. Scholars like B.Safaraliyev, G.Bakiyeva, and N.Nasrullayeva have explored the semantic classification of phraseological expressions, categorizing them into conceptual domains such as religion, legend, history, literature, geography, and national identity. Furthermore, Professor A.Mamatov has examined phraseological units from a historical-etymological standpoint, emphasizing that many idioms emerge from Uzbek cultural realities. He

also notes the influence of both related and unrelated languages on Uzbek phraseology through processes of borrowing and adaptation [3].

Indeed, the study of phraseology through a lingo-cultural lens is vital not only for understanding language in its social and historical context but also for preserving the intangible heritage encoded in expressions. Especially, in multilingual societies like Uzbekistan, analysing how idioms reflect cultural values and historical experiences enhances cross-cultural communication and deepens appreciation for the richness of the native language. In English, idioms containing names of clothing and footwear items are quite prevalent. These expressions have often existed for centuries, and in many cases, their literal ties to clothing have faded, making their meanings harder to decipher for language learners. To enhance understanding, here is given selected idioms related to garments such as hats, belts, shoes, and gloves in Uzbek and English.

1. One such idiom is **“Tighten your belt”**, which literally suggests pulling one’s belt tighter but figuratively means to reduce spending or live more frugally, usually during tough financial times.

“With rising prices, we’ll have to tighten our belts this year”.

2. **“Handle someone with kid gloves”** means to treat someone delicately or cautiously. Kid gloves were historically made of soft leather, symbolizing gentleness.

“He’s very sensitive – his colleagues always handle him with kid gloves”.

3. The idiom **“Get something under your belt”** means to acquire experience, knowledge, or an achievement. Though, it refers literally to consuming food or drink, in modern usage it refers to accomplishments.

“Once you get a few more interviews under your belt, you’ll feel more confident.”

When it comes to idioms in Uzbek language, there are many idioms related to clothing names which convey metaphorical, inner meaning.

1. **“Bir yoqadan bosh chiqarmoq”** – to be united, to be unanimous

Aka-ukalar bir yoqadan bosh chiqarib harakat qilsa, maqsadlariga yanada tez erishadilar.

2. **“To‘nini teskari kiyib oldi”** – to be obstinate without turning off Example:

Uning sovvuq muomalasi tufayli Saodat to‘nini teskari kiydi.

3. **“Do‘ppisini osmonga otdi”** – juda hursand bo‘ldi, over happy.

Example: *Farzandli bo‘lganini eshitib do‘ppisini osmonga otdi [4], [5].*

These idioms show how clothing-related expressions in English can carry rich metaphorical meanings that go far beyond their literal sense. Understanding their historical and cultural backgrounds not only enhances comprehension but also brings learners closer to the cultural mindset embedded in the language.

This study highlights the importance of idioms with adjective components in English and Uzbek, an area that remains relatively understudied. Focusing on around

ten clothing-related idioms, it explored how cultural identity shapes and is reflected in language. Despite cultural differences, many adjective-based idioms in both languages share similar meanings, often describing human qualities. Linguistic, semantic, and morphological analyses, along with insights from leading linguists, support these findings.

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